

with SCU and USG at higher N levels was caused by a higher percentage of unfilled spikelets.

The grain yield-predicting equations

for different urea materials were as follows:

$$\text{PU} : \hat{Y} = 3021 + 28.35 X - 0.1765 X^2$$

$$\text{SCU} : \hat{Y} = 3323 + 29.15 X - 0.2253 X^2$$

$$\text{USG} : \hat{Y} = 3281 + 28.99 X - 0.2253 X^2$$

where Y is expected grain yield (kg/ha) and X is kg N/ha. □

Effects of Zn application on direct-seeded rice in some alkaline soils in West Bengal

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As a part of the program to introduce modern rice varieties (MV) and optimum management practices to increase rice production in an integrated rural development project in West Bengal, we organized demonstration trials using different short-duration MVs in 1982 pre-kharif. The local farmers primarily grow a nondescript variety called IRRI that came from Bangladesh. It has short duration and fairly stable yields but is highly susceptible to many diseases and insect pests.

Nonreplicated demonstration trials were laid out in seven villages and compared IR36, IR50, and MW10 with the local IRRI.

Each variety was planted on 400 m² in each trial plot. Results from 16 trial plots grown by farmers of diverse socio-economic groups were averaged (see table). Because the local variety had Zn deficiency symptoms, Zn was applied in the trials.

Yield and ancillary characters of direct-seeded shortduration MVs and the effect of Zn application, West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)		Effective tillers/hill		Spikelets (no./panicle)		Spikelet sterility (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)		Duration (d)	
	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T
IR36	85	90	18	22	75	132	18	18	3.6	4.6	2.8	3.2	103	105
IR50	90	90	28	28	183	185	55	20	3.0	4.0	2.5	2.8	105	105
MW10	100	107	24	25	154	162	40	10	4.1	4.8	5.2	5.2	103	105
IRRI	75	82	16	18	102	105	22	12	2.7	3.0	3.0	3.2	105	107

^a C = water-sprayed plot, T = Zn-sprayed plot.

Soils varied from heavy clay to loam, pH from 7.0 to 8.0, EC_e from 0.02 to 0.18 dS/m, organic carbon from 0.17 to 0.50%, available P from 18 to 70 kg/ha, and available K from 99 to 330. Five t farmyard manure/ha and 12-11-21 kg NPK/ha were applied basally. Aldrin 5% at 35 kg/ha was applied at land preparation. Seeds pretreated with 1 g carben-dazim/kg were dibbled, 5-6 seeds/hole, at 20- × 5-cm spacing and thinned to 3 seedlings/hole 15 d after emergence. Manual weeding was done at 20 and 40 d after sowing when 25 and 13 kg N/ha were applied. ZnSO₄ at 1% was sprayed on plants 30 and 45 d after sowing as a half-plot treatment. Water was sprayed

in the other half-plot. Plots were sown from 12 May to 2 Jun 1983. Yield data were recorded from the subplot and from 10 randomly selected plants from each subplot. Each subplot was considered a replication.

All three MVs yielded more grain than IRRI. MW10 yielded more straw than the other varieties. Applying Zn decreased spikelet sterility in IR50 and MW10, but not in IR36, perhaps because IR36 flowered unevenly. Zn application did increase the number of effective tillers and spikelets per panicle in IR36. Applying 16 kg ZnSO₄/ha in two 8-kg applications increased net profit on the rice crop by \$100/ha. □

Rice ratoon crop root systems

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Ratooning, the ability of the rice plant to regenerate tillers after harvest, is affected by many main crop environmental factors and cultural practices. Of several factors that determine ratooning potential, root vigor and distribution are probably very important.

We investigated the root distribution and changes in root dry weight of an IR44 ratoon crop at the IRRI farm in 1983 wet season. Mature plants were ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm

above the ground. Immediately after, 40 kg N/ha was topdressed. During main crop harvest wooden planks were used to minimize root damage. Ten plants were randomly selected at each sampling date, and plant and soil were removed to about 20-cm depth. Roots were washed and rated for distribution, then clipped and dried at 70°C to a constant weight. Roots from the mother culms and those from the ratoon tillers were separated 42 d after harvest (DH), at ratoon flowering (53 DH), and at ratoon harvest (75 DH).

At main crop harvest and up to 35 DH, 70-80% of the roots were reddish brown. A few plants had pale brown roots at main crop harvest. The propor-

tion of black (dead) roots increased with age. Some (1 to 5%) white (new) roots developed from nodes close to the ground. A fairly high (40 to 80%) amount of dead roots was observed from 35 to 75 DH. Beyond 42 DH, most plants had well-developed white roots from ratoon tillers, but some ratoon tillers lacked roots, indicating complete dependence on the main crop roots for nutrients.

Root dry weight differed significantly during ratoon development and growth. Root dry weight declined from 0 to 14 DH (see figure) because the nutrients for initial ratoon growth are supplied by the mother culms and roots. Part of the decrease may also be attributed to the

death and decay of old roots. Root dry weight increased from 14 DH to 28 DH, and then declined gradually up to 75 DH. New roots developed 14-28 DH, but they grew very slowly. Plants exhibited roots from the ratoon tillers at 21 DH. Rooting was more profuse and rapid from lower ratoon tillers than from upper tillers. The mean dry weight of roots from ratoon tillers was 11-19% of the total dry weight at 42 DH, ratoon flowering, and harvesting.

Total root dry weight decreased after 28 DH perhaps because main crop roots were decaying as evidenced by 75 to 85% dead roots at ratoon harvest.

Ratoon tiller development in IR44 appears to depend on the main crop root system for nutrients at least up to 21 DH. Thereafter, the requirements were partially supplemented by new roots from ratoon tillers. However, the contribution of new roots seems very low. It is suggested that care be taken to avoid damaging main crop roots at harvest. □

Root production in the ratoon crop of IR44, IRRI.

Effects of N application on rice yield under drought

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We studied the interaction of N and K on rice yield in a field experiment at TNRRI, Sep 1982-Jan 1983 season. Zero, 50, 100, or 150 kg N/ha and 0, 41.5, or 83 kg K/ha with 22 kg P/ha were applied in 3 replications to IR20.

Soil was an Adanur series, very deep, noncalcareous grey brown, clay loam, with sand layers below 110 cm. Soil had pH 6.7, 2.23% organic matter, 0.11% total N, 36.0 meq CEC/100 g, 67.0 kg available P/ha, 0.45 meq exchangeable K/100 g, and 38.9% water-holding capacity.

There was an unusual drought in the Cauvery Delta during the study. We studied the effect of fertilization on rice grown under drought conditions. The crop was irrigated for only 2 wk after transplanting. Drought developed gradually. Surface irrigation was provided

Grain yield of rice under different N fertilization and drought conditions.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	2.6
50	2.1
100	2.1
150	1.9
CD	0.4

at wide intervals. Water stress was acute from heading to harvest.

Grain yield (mean of three replications) is shown in the table. Under drought conditions, N application considerably decreased yield. There also was a marginal yield decrease with increasing N application. K application did not affect rice yield. □

Evaluation of soil zinc fertility parameters for rice

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We evaluated equilibrium soil-solution Zn concentration in $\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$ (intensity, C), Zn remaining adsorbed on soil in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ (capacity, q), Zn supply parameters (unitless unified terms of intensity, capacity, and buffering capacity factors, SP), and corrected supply parameters (unitless new parameter, CSP) at 15° and 30°C and their averages as soil Zn fertility index in a pot experiment.

Twenty Mollisols were equilibrated in duplicate for 2 h with 0.01M CaCl₂ solution (soil solution ratio 1:10) at 15° and 30°C, and C was determined. Using C, q at 15° and 30°C were calculated: $q_{30^\circ\text{C}} = (K_1 \cdot C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) / (K_2 + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C})$ and $q_{15^\circ\text{C}} = (q_{30^\circ\text{C}} + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) - (C \text{ at } 15^\circ\text{C})$, where K₁ was adsorption maxima ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) and K₂ was constant relative to adsorption energy ($\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$). The K₁ = (intercept)⁻¹ and K₂ = (K₁, slope) were estimated for each soil at 15° and 30°C in a separate Zn adsorption study in the range of 5 to 30 μg added Zn/g soil from the equation (Zn adsorbed by soil, $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) = $(1/K_1) + (K_2/K_1) \cdot (\text{Zn in solution, } \mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml})^{-1}$. Expected interaction term of intensity, capacity, buffering capacity ($b = (K_2/K_1) \cdot (q_2/C_2)$,